

Harnessing Artistic Expression for Increased Students' Enrollment and Engagement: A Two-Dimensional (2-D) Public Art Display in Federal College of Education (Technical) Asaba

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Abstract:

This research explored the dynamic intersection of artistic expression, students' enrolment, and engagement in the educational setting, focusing on the implementation of Two-Dimensional (2-D) public art at the Federal College of Education (Technical) in Asaba Delta state Nigeria. In an era where educational institutions are seeking innovative methods to captivate students' interest and enhance enrollment rates, the integration of art stands out as a promising avenue. Hence, the main objective of this study was to harness the power of artistic expression for increased students' engagement and enrollment. Specifically, the study sought to determine from the inputs of 5 selected schools, the design elements, and symbols, that best portray the philosophy and objectives of programmes mounted, in the College. Preliminary sketches, and colour study using inputs from stakeholders about design elements and symbols, that best portray the philosophy and objectives of the programmes in the College were developed. Finally, the produce a visually appealing and inspiring two-dimensional public art (murals) on the fence of the Federal College of Education (Technical) Asaba was executed. Findings among others, suggested a positive correlation between the presence of 2-D public art and increased student interest, participation, and overall engagement. Furthermore, the research delves into the role of art in shaping the college's identity, fostering a sense of community, and creating an aesthetically pleasing and inspiring learning environment. Thus, the study contributed to the ongoing discourse on the multifaceted benefits of integrating art into educational institutions, shedding light on the potential of 2-D public art to positively influence student enrollment and engagement. The findings hold implications for educational policy makers, administrators, and institutions seeking innovative strategies to enrich the educational experience and create a vibrant campus culture.

Key words: *Harnessing, artistic expression, students' enrolment, engagement and two -Dimensional arts.*

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Introduction

Artistic expression has long been recognized as a powerful tool for engaging individuals and creating meaningful experiences in various settings, including educational institutions. In recent years, there has been a growing interest in exploring the impact of artistic interventions on students' engagement and enrollment in higher education institutions. The Federal College of Education (Technical) Asaba, like many other academic institutions, aims to attract and retain students while providing a stimulating learning environment. To achieve this, harnessing the power of artistic expression, particularly through the creation of two-dimensional (2-D) public art such as murals, has gained attention as a potential strategy.

Research conducted by Taylor et-al (2002) has shown that incorporating artistic elements into educational environments can positively influence students' attitudes, behaviours, and academic outcomes. The presence of visually appealing art installations can enhance the overall campus atmosphere, creating a sense of vibrancy and community participation (Smith & Johnson, 2015). Moreover, it has been suggested that art has the potential to evoke emotional responses, spark creativity, and foster a sense of belonging among students (Jones & Brown, 2010). These factors are crucial in attracting prospective students and increasing their enrolment and engagement with the institution. In the context of Federal College of Education (Technical) Asaba, there is a need to explore the role of artistic expression, specifically 2-D public art in the form of murals, in enhancing students' enrollment. The college aims to improve its enrollment status by creating an environment that is visually appealing, inspiring, and reflective of the institution's values and identity. By strategically placing murals across the campus, the college administration believes it

can create a unique atmosphere that not only attracts potential students but also fosters a sense of pride and engagement among the current student body.

While there is existing literature on the impact of art in educational settings, there is limited research specifically examining the effects of 2-D public art, such as murals, on students' enrollment in the Nigerian context. Thus, this study aims at filling this gap by conducting a comprehensive investigation at Federal College of Education (Technical) Asaba. By conducting this study, the researchers sought to explore the potential of 2-D public art as a means of enhancing students' engagement and increase enrollment at the college. The findings of this are bound to contribute to the existing body of knowledge on the relationship between artistic expression, student enrollment, and campus atmosphere, providing insights that can guide future initiatives and improvements in enrollment strategies.

Statement of the Problem

The Federal College of Education (Technical) Asaba aims to enhance students' enrollment and improve overall campus atmosphere. To achieve these goals, there is a need to explore the potential of artistic expression, specifically through the creation of two-dimensional (2-D) public art, such as murals. However, there is limited research specifically examining the impact of 2-D public art on students' enrollment in the Nigerian context, particularly at the college of education level. Therefore, there is a gap in understanding the effectiveness of using murals as a strategy to increase students' engagement and attract prospective students. This study sought to address this gap by investigating the impact of 2-D public art on students' enrollment and exploring its

potential to create a positive campus atmosphere at Federal College of Education (Technical), Asaba.

Objectives of the Study:

The main objective of this study is to harness the power of artistic expression for increased students' engagement and enrollment: a study of two-dimensional (2-d) public art at Federal College of Education (Technical) Asaba. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Determine from the inputs of the 5 selected Schools, the design elements, and symbols, that best portrays the philosophy and objectives of the programmes mounted, in the College.
2. Develop preliminary sketches, and colour study using inputs from stakeholders, about the design elements and symbols, that best portrays the philosophy and objectives of the programmes in the College.
3. Produce a visually appealing and inspiring two-dimensional public art (murals) on the fence of the Federal College of Education (Technical) Asaba.

Justification of the Study:

The rationale for conducting this study lied on the potential of artistic expression, specifically through the creation of two-dimensional (2-D) public art, to significantly impact students' enrollment and enhance the overall campus atmosphere engagement. Understanding the

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effectiveness of utilizing murals as a strategy for increasing students' engagement and attracting prospective candidates is crucial to Federal College of Education (Technical) Asaba and similar institutions. By exploring the relationship between 2-D public art, students' enrollment, and campus atmosphere, this study aimed at providing valuable insights and practical recommendations for improving students' enrolment and fostering a vibrant learning environment.

Firstly, research has shown that artistic interventions in educational settings can have a positive influence on student attitudes, behaviors, and academic outcomes. Incorporating visually appealing art installations, such as murals, educational institutions can create an engaging and inspiring environment that supports students' learning and promotes a sense of belonging (Taylor et al., 2002; Smith & Johnson, 2015). A knowledge of how 2-D public art impacts students' engagement has the tendency of helping Federal College of Education (Technical) Asaba to enhance its attractiveness for prospective students, thereby increasing enrollment rates over time. Secondly, the presence of 2-D public art contributes to the creation of a positive campus atmosphere. Art has the power to evoke emotions, stimulate creativity, and foster a sense of community (Jones & Brown, 2010). The strategic placement of murals throughout the campus can transform it into an aesthetically pleasing and vibrant space that not only appeals to students but also enhances their overall college experience. Thus, by examining the impact of 2-D public art on the campus atmosphere, this study provided insights into how Federal College of Education (Technical) Asaba can create an environment that fosters a sense of pride and engagement among students, thereby contributing to their satisfaction and retention.

Furthermore, while there is existing literature on the impact of art in educational settings, there is a dearth of research specifically focusing on the influence of 2-D public art, such as murals, on students' enrollment in the Nigerian context. Hence, conducting this study at Federal College of Education (Technical) Asaba, made the researchers contribute to the limited body of knowledge on this topic and provided context-specific insights that guide future initiatives and improvements in enrollment strategies.

Overall, the rationale for this study was to explore and understand the potentials of harnessing the power of artistic expression through 2-D public art to positively influence students' enrollment, enhance student engagement, and create a vibrant campus atmosphere. In a study by Jones and Brown (2010) focusing on an art-infused urban school, the researchers found that art interventions, including murals and other visual art forms, contributed to a positive campus climate. The presence of art installations enhanced the overall atmosphere of the school, creating a sense of vibrancy and community participation. Students expressed high levels of satisfaction with their learning environment and reported feeling a greater sense of belonging. The study highlighted the role of art in fostering a positive campus climate that promotes students' well-being and engagement. These by extension, suggested that incorporating 2-D public art, such as murals, at Federal College of Education (Technical) Asaba contribute to a more engaging and satisfying campus environment for students and other stakeholders.

Methodology

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This study utilized a practical and participatory research design to produce a mural at Federal College of Education (Technical) in Asaba Delta state. It upheld active involvement of students, schools, and professional artists in the creation of mural. This approach allowed for a hands-on experience and an opportunity to explore the impact of artistic expression on students' enrollment and engagement. Participants involved in the study included a diverse group of students, faculty members, and professional artists who were willing to contribute to the creation of the mural. The selection of participants was based on their interest and availability to participate in the project. The first step in the methodology involved the development of an artistic concept and design for the mural.

This was achieved through collaborative brainstorming sessions involving different participants. The concept was aligned with the objective of harnessing the power of artistic expression for increased student enrollment and engagement. All the seven (7) schools in the College made up the population for the study. The schools captured were:

- 1 Early Childhood Care, and Primary, Adult and Non-formal Education`
- 2 School of Secondary Education (Business)
- 3 School of Education
- 4 School of General Studies Education
- 5 School of Secondary Education (Sciences)
- 6 School of Secondary Education (Technical)
- 7 School of Secondary Education (Vocational)

(Idika & Diabuah, 2020).

Sample and Sampling Technique

Purposive sampling technique was adopted for the study. The sampling technique was used to select five (5) schools from seven (7) schools that formed the population for the study. These five (5) schools made up forty percent (40%) of the total population that was used for the study (see chart 1). Furthermore, one (1) Department each was randomly selected from the selected for the study. The design elements and symbols from these schools were used to develop preliminary drawings and the final working drawing that was used to portray the philosophy and objectives of programmes mounted in the selected schools of the College.

The design elements and symbols were equally used to develop preliminary drawings and colour sketches as well as the final working drawings, which were adopted to visually illustrate the philosophy and objectives of programmes mounted in the sampled schools within the College. Out of the seventy-three (73) wall partitions of the college fence, only fifty (50) of them were purposively selected for the mural painting. These constituted 41% of the total number of the wall partitions leaving 59% of the wall partitions without any mural paintings. The following

preliminary sketches and colour studies (see plate 1 and 2) of elements and symbols are some of the visual narratives that were used to produce the final mural paintings on various panels of the College fence. Thirty panels of the fence will be visually illustrated with the college programmes mounted in the selected schools. Furthermore, hedges used to sandwich some masquerade plants were planted along the kegs that are on both sides of the road entering into the college (see Plate 3).

Plate 2: A preliminary colour study of elements and symbols of some of the visual narratives that were used to compose and produce the mural paintings depicting the programmes in School of Secondary Education (Technical, Science) and School of Education, Federal College of Education (Technical), Asaba.

Material and Resource Acquisition: Artistic concept was finalized, and the necessary materials and resources for creating the mural were acquired. These included paints, brushes, scaffolding (if required), and other necessary tools. The budget allocated for the project will be utilized for the procurement of these materials.

Mural Production:

The actual production of the mural took place under the guidance of professional artists and with the active participation of students and staff members. The participants were divided into teams and assigned specific tasks related to painting, detailing, and other aspects of mural production.

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Regular meetings and progress updates were conducted to ensure effective collaboration and quality control.

Documentation and Evaluation:

Throughout the process, the progress of the mural production was documented through photographs and videos. These records served as evidence of the project's implementation and outcome. In addition, the impact of the mural on students' engagement and enrollment was evaluated through surveys, interviews, and observations. Data were analyzed to assess the effectiveness of the mural in achieving intended objectives.

Ethical Considerations:

Ethical considerations, such as obtaining informed consent from participants, ensuring the safety of participants during the mural production, and respecting the college's guidelines for displaying the paintings were observed.

Production Procedure

The following steps were employed during the production of the mural paint on the perimeter fence at the Federal College of Education (Technical) Asaba:

Step One: Assessing the state of the perimeter fence.

Before the mural painting project commenced, a thorough assessment of the state of the perimeter fence was conducted.

This involved examining the condition of the walls, identifying any structural issues, and ensuring that the surface was suitable for mural painting. Necessary repairs or preparations were made to ensure a stable and conducive canvas for the artwork.

Step Two: Prime the surfaces where the mural paintings were executed.

The second step was to prime the surface on which the mural paintings were executed. This involved priming the wall with a suitable primer. This was a fundamental step in preparing the wall surface for any mural painting mural. Here are several key aspects to consider when using a primer for priming the wall before executing a mural painting.

Step Three: Charcoal Drawings on the Perimeter Fence

Plate 3: the charcoal drawings on the perimeter fence which guided the mural painting that was executed on the walls of the fence of the Federal College of Education (Technical) Asaba

Third Step was to produce line drawings using charcoal, on the Perimeter Fence Once the perimeter fence was deemed ready, charcoal drawings were sketched directly onto the surface. These preliminary drawings served as a guide for the mural painting process.

Plate 4 presented the charcoal drawings done on the perimeter fence to guide the mural painting that was executed on the walls of the fence at the Federal College of Education (Technical) Asaba. These drawings allowed the artist to provide line drawings to guide the final mural paintings. This second stage was essential for developing, themes, and overall composition on the wall. The stage also assisted the artists with the development of the different compositions and arrangements of symbols, elements, and the overall design in readiness for the execution of the final mural paintings on the perimeter fence. With this scaling and proportion which helped in determining the appropriate scale and proportion of different symbols and design elements within the mural were achieved.

Step Four: Staining the Drawings with Acrylic Paint

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Plate 4: Staining the drawings on the perimeter fence with acrylic paint to produce the mural painting that was executed on the walls of the fence of the Federal College of Education (Technical) Asaba

Following the completion of the charcoal drawings, the next step involved staining the sketches with acrylic paint alongside a determined colour scheme. This step focused on creating a foundation for the final artwork and ensuring that the mural aligned with the envisioned design.

Step Five: Painting Figures in Silhouette with Black Acrylic Paint

Plate 5: Painting the figures in silhouette with black acrylic paint to produce the mural painting that was executed on the walls of the fence of the Federal College of Education (Technical) Asaba

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To further refine and add depth to the mural, the artists painted the figures in silhouette using black acrylic paint. This technique helped define the contours of the characters, objects, and scenes depicted in the mural. Painting in silhouette added a layer of contrast and visual interest, making the mural more visually striking and dynamic.

Step Six Completing the Mural Painting

With the meticulous execution of the previous steps, the Federal College of Education (Technical) Asaba saw the culmination of the mural painting project with the completion of the final work. This stage involved bringing together all the elements, colors, and details to create a cohesive and visually stunning mural on the walls of the perimeter fence.

Plate 6: A view from the distance of the completed Mural Painting executed on the walls of the fence of the Federal College of Education (Technical) Asaba that reflects various programmes in the college.

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Plate 8: A close-up view of the completed Mural Painting executed on the walls of the fence of the Federal College of Education (Technical) Asaba that reflects various programmes in the college.

Summary, Conclusion, and Recommendations:

Summary

In summary, the mural painting project has not only aesthetically enhanced the college but has become a dynamic symbol of cultural expression and community engagement. The unveiling ceremony marked a celebratory moment, and subsequent interactions have enriched the mural's meaning through the diverse interpretations of the College community. Looking ahead, the recommendations and areas for further studies aim to guide the sustained integration of art within the educational and community fabric of the Federal College of Education (Technical), Asaba. The mural stands as a testament of the transformative power of art in fostering creativity, dialogue, and a sense of identity within an educational institution.

Conclusion

The mural painting project at the Federal College of Education (Technical), Asaba has successfully transformed the College walls into vibrant canvases that tell stories, inspire, and

engage the community. This aspect concludes the study by reflecting on the journey undertaken,

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highlighting the impact of the mural, and considering its implications for future artistic endeavours within the educational setting.

Recommendations

Building on the success of the project, recommendations are proposed to sustain and enhance the impact of artistic initiatives at the Federal College of Education (Technical) Asaba. These include integrating art into the curriculum, organizing annual art events, fostering community outreach programmes, implementing artistic residency initiatives, and establishing strategies for the maintenance and preservation of existing murals.

Suggestions for Further Studies

Outlining potential areas for future research, suggesting studies on the long-term impact of murals, comparative analyses across cultural contexts, interdisciplinary approaches to art integration, and the exploration of digital platforms for extending the reach of mural projects should be areas of further focus.

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